

Analysis of Offences Relating to Public Servants

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Abstract

The public servants serve in a country are vital role when they normalize for the interests of country. The public servants must know respective laws, rules and regulations, procedures so that they can serve their duties easily and systematically. There are offences committed by the public servants and offences are committing by other persons against public servants. The objectives of this paper are to understand the offences and penalties relating to public servants, to refrain committing the offences by public servants and to prevent committing the offences by other persons against public servants. Actions in accordance with procedure and effective actions are core for the progresses of the country. If the public servants knew the above mentioned respective laws, rules, regulations and procedures, they can serve their functions of different parts, smoothly.

1. INTRODUCTION

The public servants serve in a country are vital role when they normalize for the interests of country. The public servants perform in their respective sectors of different ministries or organizations. The public servants must know respective laws, rules and regulations, procedures so that they can serve their duties easily and systematically. There are so many criminal offences about public servants. Among them, I want to present some offences committed by the public servants and some offences are committing by other persons against public servants. Actions in accordance with procedure and effective actions are core for the progresses of the country. If the public servants knew the above mentioned respective laws, rules, regulations and procedures, they can serve their functions of different parts, smoothly and effectively.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this paper are as follows;

- To understand the offences and penalties relating to public servants
- To refrain committing the offences by public servants and
- To prevent committing the offences by other persons against public servants.

2.1 What is Public Servant?

According to section 21 of the Penal Code, the word “Public Servant” denotes a person falling under any of the descriptions hereinafter following namely:

First - Every covenanted servant of the Government:

Second - Every commissioned Officer in the Defense Services:

Third - Every Judge:

- Fourth-** Every officer of a Court of Justice whose duty it is, as such officer, to investigate or report on any matter of law or fact, or to make, authenticate, or keep any document, or to take charge or dispose of any property, or to execute any judicial process, or to administer any oath, or to interpret, or to preserve order in the Court: and every person specially authorized by a court of justice to perform any of such duties;
- Fifth -** Every juryman, assessor, or administrator of ward or village-tract assisting a Court of Justice or public servant;
- Sixth -** Every arbitrator or other person to whom any cause or matter has been referred for decision or report by any Court of Justice, or by any other competent public authority;
- Seventh-** Every person who holds any office by virtue of which he is empowered to place or keep any person in confinement;¹
- Eighth -** Every officer of Government whose duty it is, as such officer, to prevent offences, to give information of offences, to bring offenders to justice, or to protect the public health, safety or convenience
- Ninth-** Every officer whose duty it is, as such officer, to take, receive, keep or expend any property on behalf of Government, or to make any survey, assessment or contract on behalf of Government, or to execute any revenue-process, or to investigate, or to report, on any matter affecting the pecuniary interests of Government, or to make, authenticate or keep any document relating to the pecuniary interests of Government, or to prevent the infraction of any law for the protection of the pecuniary interests of Government, and every officer in the service or pay of the Government or remunerated by fees or commission for the performance of any public duty (or every member of the Government);
- Tenth-** Every officer whose duty it is, as such officer, to take, receive, keep or expend any property, to make any survey or assessment, or to levy any rate or tax for any secular common purpose of any village, town or district, or to make, authenticate or keep any document for the ascertaining of the rights of the people of any village, town or district;
- Eleventh –** Every person who holds any office in virtue of which he is empowered to prepare, punish, maintain or revise an electoral roll or to conduct an election or part of an election.²

3. OFFENCES COMMITTED BY THE PUBLIC SERVANTS

There are so many offences committed by the public servants but I would like to describe some offences as like section 161 to 165, 166, 167, 409 of the Penal code and

¹ Penal Code

² Penal Code

section 55, 56, 57 of the Anti – Corruption law. Public servants must know these offences because they shall refrain above mentioned sections with action according to these Laws. But, sections 161 to 165 are not explained in detail.

Sections 161 to 165 are concerned with corruption enacted in the Penal Code but these offences must action according to Anti- Corruption Law (Special Law) because Special Law overrides Penal Code (General Law). Firstly, I would like to discuss section 3 (h), section 3 (i) and section 3 (j) of Anti – Corruption Law before section 55, 56, 57 of Anti – Corruption Law so that I want to understand about section 55, 56 and 57 of Anti – Corruption Law.

According to section 3 (h) of Anti- corruption Law, **Political Post-holder** means deputy ministers or the equivalent rank and above who currently hold political posts, section 3 (i) of Anti- corruption Law, **Senior Official** means the Director General or Managing Director served as the Head of Services Personnel of the Government department, Government organization or the person who is in such similar rank, or the member of the Director, Board, Committee of the Company, Board, Corporation or other organization owned by the State or State and Private Joint Venture or the person who is in such similar rank. In this expression, the temporary servant in such post shall also be included and section 3 (j) of Anti- corruption Law, **Competent Authority** means the public servant, foreign public servant, person who possesses the political post, senior official or administrator or representative of any public organization.

3.1 Punishments under Anti-Corruption Law

According to section 55 of Anti – corruption law, any person who possesses the political post commits the bribery, on conviction, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 15 years, and shall also be liable.

According to section 56 of Anti – corruption law, any other competent authority except the person who possess the political post commits the bribery, on conviction, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 10 years, and shall also be liable to fine.

According to section 57 of Anti – corruption law, any other person except the person who possesses the political post the competent authority commits the bribery, on conviction, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 7 years, and shall also be liable to fine.³

3.2 Duties

According to section 10 of Civil service Personnel Law, the service personnel is responsible for:

- (a) Allegiance to the Union;
- (b) Abiding the provisions contained in the Constitution and the existing Laws;
- (c) Performing the interest of the Union and its citizens with regard;

³ Anti – corruption law

- (d) Maintaining and safeguarding of the state-owned properties and finance not to be lost and misappropriated;
- (e) Carrying out the assigned duties and responsibilities efficiently;
- (f) abiding the Rules, Regulations, by-laws, orders, directives made by this Law and specific workplace disciplines, orders and directives particularly stipulated by the respective Service Personnel Organization;
- (g) Being free from party politics;
- (h) Attending the trainings stipulated by the Civil Service Board;
- (i) Avoiding from depravity and misconduct;
- (j) Avoiding from misappropriation of vested authority according to the duty;
- (k) Avoiding from bribery;
- (l) Providing service to the public respectfully.⁴

In the case of U Chit Htwe Vs The Union of Myanmar, Minister of Education, Naypyitaw, 2015, p 31, U Chit Htwe applied to issue the writ of mandamus upon the Union Minister, Minister of Education according to section 16 (A) (2) of the Union Judiciary Law. U Chit Htwe is a Civil Service Personnel in Ministry of Education. Civil Service Personnel must obey the duties and obligations to serve enacted in section 10 (e) and rules, regulations, orders, directives and departmental regulations regulated by their department to obey enacted in section 10 (f) of Civil Service personnel Law. The Union Minister punished U Chit Htwe as punishment removal according to section 53 of Civil Service Personnel Law because he omitted to obey order, directives issued from his department and serving obligations dutifully. Union Minister determined to the applicant, U Chit Htwe according to the Law and Procedure. Finally, the court rejected this application by U Chit Htwe because Union Minister determined it according to the Law and procedure.⁵

3.3 Penalties

According to section 53 Civil Service Personnel Law, In holding departmental inquiries, one of the following penalties or more than one penalty may be imposed in accord with the rules, regulations and by-laws:

- (a) Censure;
- (b) Withholding of increment;
- (c) Withholding of promotion;
- (d) Reduction of pay within pay scale;
- (e) Reduction to a lower post;
- (f) Recovery of wholly or partially lost value caused by negligence or breach of orders and directives;

⁴ Civil Service Personnel Law

⁵ Myanmar Rulings, 2015, P 31

- (g) Not permitting to enjoy full pay or not determining such term as the term of duty for the term of suspension from duty;
- (h) Removal from the post
- (i) Dismissal from being services personnel.⁶

3.4 Public Servant Disobeying Law with Intent to Cause injury to Any Person

According to Section 166 of the Penal Code, whoever being a public servant, knowingly disobeys any direction of the law as to the way in which he is to conduct himself as such public servant, intending to cause, or knowing it to be likely that he will, by such disobedience, cause injury to any person, shall be punished with simple imprisonment for a term which may extend to one year, or with fine, or with both.⁷

Illustration: A, being an officer directed by law to take property in execution in order to satisfy a decree pronounced in Z's favour by a Court of Justice, knowingly disobeys that direction of Law with the knowledge that he is likely thereby to cause injury to Z. A has committed the offence defined in this section.

3.5 Public Servant Framing an Incorrect Document With Intent to Cause Injury

According to Section 167 of the Penal Code, whoever being a public servant, and being, as such public servant, charged with the preparation or translation of any document, frames or translates that document in a manner which he knows or believes to be incorrect, intending thereby to cause or knowing it to be likely that he may thereby cause injury to any person, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

3.6 Committing of Criminal Breach of Trust by Public servant

According to section 409 of the Penal Code, whoever being in any manner entrusted with property, or with any dominion over property, in his capacity of a public servant or in the way of his business as a banker, merchant, factor, broker, attorney or agent, commits criminal breach of trust in respect of that property shall be punished with imprisonment of twenty years, or with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to ten years, and shall also be liable to fine.⁸

In the case of U Htay Lwin Vs The Union of Myanmar par 2 , 2010, p 2, U Htay Lwin charged by section 409 of penal Code because of misappropriation of government's property. The Court sentenced to imprisonment for 10 years the accused respectively. U Htay Lwin filed to appeal to the court of Pango Division, the court sentenced to instead of imprisonment from 10 years to 3 years to him. Again, this order filed as revision to the Supreme Court but the court dismissed⁹ as summary. Again, this order filed as special appeal.

⁶ Civil Service Personnel Law

⁷ Penal Code

⁸ Penal Code

⁹ Myanmar Rulings, 2010, P 2

Finally, the court confirmed the orders of divisional and supreme court and dismissed the revision.¹⁰

In the case of U Thein par 5 Vs The Union of Myanmar, 1967, p 99, the accused are police officer and policeman in this case. The accused did not action according to Law and police manual and they concealed properties of deceased's persons when the people accident, unfortunately. They omit the duty and did cursed offence. The court sentenced to imprisonment for 7 years, 5 years, 4 years respectively according to section 409 of Penal Code.¹¹

4. OFFENCES ARE COMMITTING BY OTHER PERSONS AGAINST PUBLIC SERVANTS

There are many offences about committing the offences by other persons against public servants but I would like to describe some offences as like section 152, 332, 333, 353. Public servants must know these offences because they can action the offenders according to Law effectively.

4.1 Assaulting or Obstructing Public Servant when suppressing Riot, etc.

According to Section 152 of the Penal Code, whoever assaults or threatens to assault, or obstructs or attempts to obstruct, any public servant in the discharge of his duty as such public servant, in endeavouring to disperse an unlawful assembly, to suppress a riot or affray, or uses or threatens, or attempts to use criminal force to such public servant, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

4.2 Hurt, Grievous Hurt and Assault or Criminal Force against Public Servants Voluntarily Causing Hurt to Deter Public Servant from his duty

According to Section 332 of the Penal Code, Whoever voluntarily cause hurt to any person being a public servant in the discharge of his duty as such public servant, or with intend to prevent or deter that person or any other public servant from discharge of his duty as such public servant, or in consequence of anything done or attempted to be done by that person in the lawful discharge of his duty as such public servant, shall be punished with¹² imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

4.3 Voluntarily Causing Grievous Hurt to Deter Public Servant from his duty

According to Section 333 of the Penal Code, Whoever voluntarily cause hurt to any person being a public servant in the discharge of his duty as such public servant, or with intend to prevent or deter that person or any other public servant from discharge of his duty as such public servant, or in consequence of anything done or attempted to be done by that person in the lawful discharge of his duty as such public servant, shall be punished with

¹⁰ Myanmar Rulings, 2010, P 2

¹¹ Myanmar Rulings, 1967, P 99

¹² Penal Code

imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to three years, or with fine, or with both.

4.4 Assault or Criminal Force to deter public servant from discharge of his duty

According to Section 353 of the Penal Code, whoever assault or uses criminal force to any person being a public servant in the execution of his duty as such public servant, or with intent to prevent or deter that person from discharging his duty as such public servant, or in consequence of anything done or attempted to be done by such person in the lawful discharge of his duty as such public servant, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to two years, or with fine, or with both.¹³

In the case of Mg Kyaw Myint Vs The Union of Myanmar, 1968, p 261, this case is criminal case for revision by Mg Kyaw Myint because the original court sentenced to imprisonment for 3 months, 2 years and 1 years to Mg Kyaw Myint by combining, respectively because students including Mg Kyaw Myint did civil disobedience, surrounded the classroom and threatened to the guard (Arsiraman) of this school. So the original court action them by section 153, 447 and 353 of the Penal Code. Finally, the revisional court dismissed the application of Mg Kyaw Myint.¹⁴

5. COMPARISON OF PUNISHMENTS

The punishments of Section 166, 167, 409, 152, 332, 333 and 353 of Myanmar Penal Code and Singapore Penal Code as an example mention as follows ;

Table 1: Comparison of prison¹⁵

Section	Myanmar	Singapore
166	1 year or fine or both	1 year or fine or both
167	3 years or fine or both	3 years or fine or both
409	20 years or 10 years and fine	20 years and fine
152	3 years or fine or both	8 years or fine or both
332	3 years or fine or both	7 years and fine or Caning
333	10 years and fine	15 years and fine or Caning
353	2 years or fine or both	4 years or fine or both

¹³ Penal Code

¹⁴ Myanmar Rulings, 1968, P 261

¹⁵ Myanmar Penal Code and Singapore Penal Code

6. FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Currently, sections 161 to 165 of Penal Code are not repealed about corruption and bribery but these offences action according to Anti- Corruption Law (Special law). Measures have not been effectively about these offences and corruption remains as serious problem in Myanmar. Enforcement of corruption and bribery is less than other public servants offences in Myanmar. Some of the provisions of this Code about public servant offences are outdated and ineffective (eg, It is necessary to enhance punishments for imprisonment and fine). So, section 161 to 165 of Penal Code about corruption and bribery must action according to Anti-corruption Law (Special Law). And it is needed for actions effectively about all offences mentioned above.

Corruption and bribery enacted in Penal Code but these offences must action and enforce according to Anti-corruption Law (Special Law) effectively. Punishments shall also enhance in other offences relating to public servants as like Singapore. Sanctions must ask in proceedings according to law and procedures. Criminal Proceedings must do in accordance with procedure correctly so that these offences can action effectively.

7. CONCLUSION

The role of public servants is very critical role in the building of a nation. They must understand the offences and penalties relating to public servants. If they knew these legal knowledge, they will reframe committing the offences about public servants and prevent committing the offences by other person against public servants. All Civil Service Personnel are also public servant and government servant. Every public servant is not Civil Service Personnel but every Civil Service Personnel is public servant. All Civil Service Personnel must abide Civil Service Personnel Law and Rules. Besides, they must abide the provisions of Penal Code and other existing Laws. It can as sure as gun promote good governance and deveopment for our nation if the public servant abides the provisions of Penal Code, Civil Service Personnel Law and Rules and other existing Laws.¹⁶

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¹⁶ Penal Code, U Kyaw Sein, 2019